

ISSN: 2456-5474

RNI No. UPBIL/2016/68367

VOL.- X , ISSUE- III April - 2025
Innovation The Research Concept

Viksit Bharat @2047 : The Challenges Ahead

Paper Id : 20128 Submission Date : 2025-04-12 Acceptance Date : 2025-04-20 Publication Date : 2025-04-25

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.15559593

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>

U. K. Jha

Professor
Political Science
D.P.B.S. P.G. College,
Anup Shahr
Bulandshahr, Uttar
Pradesh, India

Abstract

The idea of Viksit Bharat @2047 is a grand initiative of P.M. Modi to transform India from a developing to a developed country by the centenary year of its independence. It is a vision to promote the kind of development which is both inclusive as well as sustainable. The focus of the initiative is not only on economic growth but also on social progress, environmental sustainability, good governance and bringing all round improvement in quality of human lives. The strategy is to harness the power of the youths both as “the agent of change” as well as “the beneficiaries of change” and adopt innovative practices and new technologies to streamline the process of development. However, the path of development is beset with numerous challenges in the way which makes it difficult to turn the vision into a reality. This paper is an attempt to explore and identify the challenges in the way of ‘Viksit Bharat’ and what can be done to turn the dream into a reality.

Keywords Viksit Bharat, Amrit Kaal, Human Development, Poverty, Inequality, Hunger, Debt Burden.

Introduction

The beginning of the viksit bharat initiative was made by P.M. Modi on December 11, 2023 by addressing via video conferencing the voice of youth workshops organized at Raj Bhawana across the country. In his address the P.M. said that it was right time (Amrit Kaal) when the country was going to take a quantum leap on the path of development. Describing the glorious struggle for freedom as a source of motivation, he urged every institution and every individual for channelizing their energy towards achieving the goal of Viksit Bharat. Describing the youth power of the country as “agent” as well as “beneficiaries” of change, he stressed moulding the voice of country's youth into the policy strategy for building a developed India. He underlined the fact that the roadmap of progress will not be decided by the government alone but by the active participation of every citizen of the country.(1)

During the last two decades of Modi government several path-breaking policies and programmes have been launched to transform India's development landscape. The Goods and Services Tax (GST) reform, the Unified Payment Interface (UPI), Direct Benefit Transfer Scheme (DBT), Make in India programme, Start-up Programme, Skill India Mission, National Logistics Policy and several other programmes indicate the seriousness with which the government is trying to push India at the top of the development ladder. We have today become the fifth largest economy of the world. And yet we fail miserably on several parameters used internationally to measure the level of development of a country. There are multifold challenges in the way of achieving the goal of Viksit Bharat

Objective of study

The objective of this study is to understand and analyse the vision of viksit bharat, how this vision is different from the western model of development, what are the obstacles in the way and what can be done to turn this vision into a reality. It would be helpful to our policy makers to frame such policies which are helpful in achieving the difficult goal of making India a developed country by the year 2047.

Review of Literature

Since the vision of Viksit Bharat is a recent phenomena, there is not much literature available on this theme. However, the researcher has tried his best to consult whatever resources are available in online or offline mode. The methodology of the study is basically descriptive and analytical.

Main Text

The challenges and obstacles in the way of Viksit Bharat are numerous which can be identified as follows-

Poor Quality of Human Resource

In this age of globalization and competitive environment , the quality of human resource has become a crucial factor for transforming the development landscape of a country. Unfortunately, however, we lag behind many countries of the world on this front. According to UNDP Human Development Report (HDR) 2023-24, our Human Development Index (HDI) score is 0.644 which places us at 134th position out of 193 countries and territories. We rank below even our small neighbouring countries like Sri Lanka, Maldives, Bhutan and Bangladesh and fell into the medium human development category. (2)

It is worthy to mention that HDI is a metric used by UNDP to measure a country's average achievements in three basic aspects of development : health, knowledge and standard of living. And our poor performance on all these fronts indicate that we need to do a lot for improving the quality of our human resource.

Poverty and Inequality

Despite overall reduction in the level of extreme poverty over the years , it still remains a major challenge in our country. According to World Bank Report 2024, almost 129 million Indians are living in extreme poverty on less than \$2.15 (about Rs.181) a day. This is down from 431 million in 1990. However, with a higher poverty standard of \$6.85 (about Rs.576) per day – the poverty threshold for middle-income countries- more Indians are living below the poverty line in 2024, than in 1990, primarily driven by population growth.(3)

According to Global Hunger Index (GHI) 2024, our rank is 105th out of 127 countries. It is mentionworthy here that GHI is a tool used by international humanitarian agencies to measure and rank hunger at global , regional and national levels , reflecting multiple dimensions of hunger at global, regional, and national levels, reflecting multiple dimensions of hunger over time. The formula used to determine each nation's GHI is undernourishment, child stunting, child wasting and child mortality. Our GHI score is 27.3 which puts us behind our neighbouring countries like Sri Lanka, Nepal, Myanmar and Bangladesh.(4)

Besides poverty, inequality is a big challenge. According to a study conducted at **World Inequality Lab**, India is faced with extreme level of inequality compared to international standards. The study entitled "**Income and wealth Inequality in India (1922-2023) : The Rise of Billionaire Raj**" points out that between 2014-15 and 2022-23, the rise of top end inequality has been particularly pronounced in terms of wealth concentration. By 2022-23, top 1% income and wealth shares (22.6% and 40.1%) are their highest historical levels and India's top 1% income share is among the very highest in the world.(5)

In gender inequality also our rank is still unsatisfactory .In 2022, we ranked 108 out of 193 countries on the Gender Inequality Index (GII) up from 122 but still far behind the developed countries. Moreover, caste-based inequality is still a common form of inequality , where people are treated differently based on their caste and social status.

Least Joyful Nation

The Well-being Research Centre at the University of Oxford publishes the 'World Happiness Report' in partnership with Gallup, the UN Sustainable Development Solutions Network and an independent editorial board every year around March 20 as part of the International Day of Happiness Celebration. The happiness level of a country is calculated using a combination of data from the Gallup World Pole and a series of variables like GDP per capita, social support, healthy life expectancy , freedom, generosity, corruption etc.. According to the World Happiness Report 2024 India ranks 126th out of 143 countries. This places us amongst the world's least joyful nations , and below our neighbouring countries of Nepal, Bangladesh and China.(6)

Heavy Debt Burden

As of 2024, India's debt to GDP ratio stands at approximately 83.1%. It marks a significant increase from the pre-pandemic level, where the ratio hovered around 69% until 2018. The surge in public debt of the Central Government stood at 173 lakh crore rupees, more than double the 86 lakh crore rupees recorded in March 2020. Despite efforts to reign in the fiscal deficit of 4.9 per cent of GDP for 2024-25, the debt is projected to rise to 181.6 lakh rupees by March 2025. State Governments also contribute significantly to the national debt accounting 33% of total public debt. Their outstanding liabilities were 82.2 lakh crore rupees at the end of financial year 2023-24. (7)

India's current debt-to-GDP ratio is higher than the average for emerging market and middle-income economies, which stands at around 70%. High debt levels can lead to several negative outcomes, including higher borrowing costs, currency market instability and increased inflation expectations. These factors can reduce government spending on essential areas, ultimately impacting economic growth

Conclusion

Looking at the overall scenario, it is obvious that despite best of efforts made by our government we still fare badly on various parameters of development which makes it difficult to achieve the goal of Viksit Bharat by the year 2047. Our poor quality of human resource, poverty and inequality, very low level of happiness, heavy debt burden etc. are the major challenges requiring herculean efforts both at governmental as well as the societal levels to resolve the problems and pave the way for a viksit bharat. We need a sustained growth rate of around 8% for the next two decades to come at par with the developed countries. There is also a need to improve the training and skill of our youths as per the requirement of new technological innovations by strengthening infrastructures at our schools and colleges and designing our curriculum as per the requirement of the modern age.

References

1. Ministry of Education (11 Dec.2023). PM launches 'Viksit Bharat@2047: Voice of youth'. PIB Delhi. <https://pib.gov.in./PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=1985077>.
2. UNDP (2024). HUMAN DEVELOPMENT REPORT 2023-24: Breaking the gridlock : Reimagining cooperation in a polarized world. New York. P.290
3. World Bank. World Development Report 2024 : The Middle Income Trap. (English). Washington, D.C. : World Bank Group. <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/099080>.
4. Welthungerhilfe, Concern Worldwide and IFHV (October 2024). Global Hunger Index 2024 : How Gender Justice can advance Climate Resilience. Bonn/ Berlin/Dublin// Bochum. <https://www.globalhungerindex.org#GHI2024>.
5. Bharti, N.K., Chancel, L. and Somanchi A.(2024). Income and Wealth Inequality in India 1922-2023: The rise of the Billionaire Raj. Working Paper, World Inequality Lab. . https://www.worldinequalitylab_WP2024_09_Income-and-Wealth-Inequality-in-India.
6. Halliwell, J.F., Layard, R., Sachs, J.D., De Neve, J.E.Aknin, L.B. & Wang, S. (Ed.) (2024). World Happiness Report 2024. University of Oxford : Well-being Research Centre. (ISBN 978-1-7348080-7-0).
7. Department of Economic Affairs (27 June 2024) : Status Paper on Government Debt, Govt. of India. <https://dea.gov.i>